

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF HIGH-QUALITY TEACHING OF THE DISCIPLINE "SPEECH SCIENCE" TO STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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***Abstract.** The given article presents the essence of speech culture in "speech therapy training" of students in the system of higher education, the quality of the scientific direction which is largely determined by the skill of the teacher, as well as information that can serve as a basis for ensuring advanced and high-quality education in the future training and education of future specialists.*

***Keywords:** speech, sound, diagnostics, inclusive education, curriculum, educational standard.*

It is important to suggest that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", adopted on September 23, 2020, is the scientific and methodological basis for reforming the system of continuous education in our country, and the task of preparing a perfect personality and a mature qualified competitive specialist is relevant.. It is impossible to prepare mature personnel without thoroughly mastering the specified professional knowledge, skills and competencies. Educational activities to educate the younger generation, which is the future of independent Uzbekistan, are purposeful activities aimed at educating and training a person in order to provide opportunities for successful work.

Definitely, in terms of developing educational activities in all aspects, determining the content of personnel training based on priority tasks, the content and conditions for training specialists in accordance with international quality standards, revising specialties by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On measures for the further development of the higher education system", it is shown that the main attention is paid to the training of high-quality personnel based on a systematic increase in productivity and qualifications, the introduction of modern technologies in the educational process; SES (State Educational Standard), qualification requirements, working curricula and programs in educational institutions are one of the factors determining the development of our country, and require an approach to this issue based on a special approach.

At present time improving the quality of education in higher education institutions, developing criteria for assessing students in accordance with the requirements of the time, providing freedom to leading higher education institutions, based on the introduction of independent, modern innovative technologies in educational areas and specialties, the implementation of the curriculum and programs that encourage students to think, are important in solving the problem.

The increase in admission quotas for special pedagogy (defectology) in higher education institutions is due to the growing popularity of speech therapy services among the population.

Accordingly, the demand for speech therapists in preschool and secondary educational institutions is growing.

The concept of developing the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan also includes a systemic reform of education, training of independently thinking personnel, modernization of higher education, the introduction of innovative educational technologies in science, the gradual transfer of the educational process to credit-modular system, the introduction of advanced standards of higher education in accordance with international standards, including a number of measures, activities aimed at forming practical learning skills focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge.

These decisions affect not only the education system, but also the development of all spheres of society. Based on the tasks defined in the concept, planning work on developing an effective system for implementing electronic textbooks and multimedia tools based on new information and communication and innovative technologies is a requirement of the times. Call on future speech therapists to take these important aspects into account when training personnel in connection with the problems of obtaining and processing information on psychological processes (perception, attention, memory, mental activity, emotions, spatial imagination) of children with speech defects. Serious attention must be paid to high-quality training of personnel.

Nowadays not only in our country, but also in other countries, we can observe a significant increase in the number of children with special educational needs. This situation leads to an increase in demand for a narrow circle of specialists, in particular, for special educators: speech therapists, oligophrenic pedagogues, deaf teachers, dyslexic teachers and other specialists.

Additionally, the organization of the pedagogical process with various manifestations of children with special educational needs differs from the process in general education institutions. In this case, the qualification requirements for special educators will change, that is, they will have to organize the educational process taking into account the capabilities of children with physical or mental disabilities. According to V.A. Slastenin, "Education is not a process of "transfer" of ready-made knowledge by a teacher to students, but the relationship between a teacher and students; the implementation of the pedagogical process with the aim of personal development; is a process of stimulating and controlling the external and internal activities of a student". The future of our country is in the hands of competent young people, and their full response to all the needs of our country depends on how much the workers in the field of education have and respect their professional potential at a high level. Our independent country, moving forward with progressive steps, needs educated, mature and comprehensively developed people. It is clear that the education system requires employees to keep up with the times and conduct their activities in harmony with the news. World pedagogical experience has confirmed that modern pedagogical technologies have unlimited opportunities to interest students in subjects and increase their activity in independent activities. Educational technology, designed to achieve the same high result in an educational institution, means a set of content and methods of organizing students' activities, and not methodology, since it answers the question "How to teach?". Methodology is a process that ensures diversity and variability of ways to implement theoretical rules, but does not mean a guarantee of achieving the goal. In other words, the methodology does not promise the teacher guaranteed results. The methodology provides answers to the questions "What to teach? ", "Why to teach? and "How to teach? ". Accordingly, methodology is an activity within a specific academic discipline. Pedagogical possibilities of using innovative technologies for the effective organization

of training of future speech therapists based on the principles of consistency and continuity during practice are comprehensively studied. This is one of the forms of optimal organization of training, education and upbringing of specialized subjects based on innovative technologies. The word "Innovation" is borrowed from the English language and means "update", "mastering", "implementation of something new", and the word "new" is the core of this concept. It seems that the concept of "innovation" reflects a specific situation. Based on this, we can say that innovation is an activity aimed at changing the internal structure of a specific system. If we talk about educational innovations, this concept is also called "Innovative Education" and was first mentioned in the "Club of Rome". "An important task is to form students as independent, responsible, comprehensively developed individuals, their successful socialization and creation of an innovative educational environment for their preparation as personnel taking place in the labor market. After all, its adaptation to international standards is an important factor in the successful socialization of young people in society. An effective solution to this problem, in turn, requires the modernization of the educational process as an integral system.

At present time due to the connection with one or another component of the educational process, the following technologies of pedagogical innovations are being introduced into practice:

- Innovative approach to educational content;
- Teaching methods;
- Organization of the educational process;
- Planned management of the education system.

These innovative technologies not only increase the effectiveness of training, but also create the opportunity to successfully prepare future speech therapists for innovative activities.

Improvement of innovative education requires the introduction of existing teaching methods and new large-scale interactive methods, pedagogical technologies. In this case, innovative educational technologies used in teaching Speech Science are divided into the following types:

- by area of activity: technologies used in managing the educational system in the pedagogical process;
- by classification of changes introduced: basic (radical) combined innovations, modified technologies.
- by scale of changes: network (local), modular, mastered technologies.

It is known that professional training of students in higher education is formed in the process of a comprehensive system of correctional work. One of the tasks of higher education is to prepare a new generation of specialists with broad basic knowledge, enterprising and adaptable to the changing demands of the labor market and technology. In addition to training, students learn the secrets of professional virtue: taking into account the psychological abilities of children in the work process, convincing them of their own strengths, awakening enthusiasm for activity, the ability to attract full attention during the presentation of the topic, ways of memorizing the topic (exercise, use of visual aids, independent work, conversation, game technology, innovative technology) and pay special attention to a competency-based approach in preparing future defectologists for professional activity. The textbook "Speech therapy" created by Lola Rakhimovna Muminova, a scientist, doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor, youth trainer who served in Uzbekistan, the founder of the science of "Speech therapy", instructions for "Organization of correctional speech therapy work in special preschool institutions for children

with severe speech defects", "Speech therapy album for speech assessment and development", "Speech assessment and teaching of preschoolers whose speech is not fully developed", a methodological manual and a number of textbooks co-authored not only for future speech therapists studying in the higher education system, but also for special educators, speech therapists working in the education system, teachers, psychologists, they serve as a methodological basis for the elimination and correction of speech and mental development disorders in children. Our everyday speech, behavior are a means of exchanging ideas. The pursuit of a certain goal is a constant feature of speech, the result of a certain impact on the interlocutor, because we never speak without a specific goal and objective. Our speech also always reflects our feelings and our attitude to the subject we are talking about. When we speak, we persuade, explain, challenge, approve, laugh, reveal secrets, reprimand, etc.

It is not a secret that speech culture is an integral part of universal human culture and determines the high culture of a person. Today, when spiritual and educational reforms are defined as a priority direction of state policy in our country, the issues of speech culture are more relevant than ever. Teaching young people to think freely and independently through teacher's speech, instilling speech entrepreneurship is the main task in educational institutions. Public speaking is a special skill. Real speakers achieve their speaking skills as a result of constant work on their language and speech, as well as a result of natural abilities. Since ancient times, public speaking has been interpreted as a special skill, an art, as a special, unique human ability. In this regard, it is necessary to distinguish eloquence from speech culture, because not every form of oral speech is eloquence in the sense of the ability to speak.

It is known that oral speech is a process of communication. In recent years, our opinion has been confirmed by the fact that speech is considered a way of communication between people through language. Language is a social phenomenon characterized by community, and speech is particular, and both serve society. Pronunciation is very important in oral speech. It is impossible to imagine mastering speech without fluency of pronunciation. In oral speech, the mind controls the construction of sentences. Memory plays a large role in this. If the memory is weak, the structure of sentences and phrases in oral speech will not be connected logically and grammatically. The formation and improvement of oral speech largely depends on the improvement of written speech. If written speech is not at a high level, oral speech will not be as desired. In written speech, there is a full opportunity to choose and use linguistic means. Written speech can be edited at will. Written speech does not cause such excitement as oral speech. The speaker (teacher) delivers a thoughtful speech, without rushing. For this reason, written speech is more fluent, clear and coherent than oral speech. The written expression of any style, be it artistic, scientific or official, is called an essay. It is difficult to imagine the activity of an orator (teacher) who does not have a command of oral and written speech. The oral and written speech of a teacher is stable and firm, it is always thought out and written down. Not a single famous orator has risen to a high position without improving his written speech. Written speech directly affects the development of oral speech. Oral speech develops mainly on the basis of written speech. Written exercises are similar to thinking exercises. Thinking about a fact or event is improved with the help of written exercises. The richness of speech is determined by these possibilities of language, i.e. by the extent to which this richness is reflected in it. The speech is rich if it contains various linguistic means. Everyone can ensure the richness of their speech if they pay attention to their speech, if they feel responsible for creating speech.

Thus, the concepts of language and speech, language culture and speech culture, as well as language richness and speech richness differ from each other. Based on the above, the following conclusions can be made:

Compliance with the norms of speech culture and literary language is the responsibility of every citizen;

The course "Speech Culture" should be included in the curriculum of all areas of higher education institutions.

It is necessary to organize broadcasts on radio and television programs on speech culture, manners and the basics of public speaking.

By summarizing it should be suggested that such qualities as sincerity, politeness, courtesy, respect for others are the reason that students listen to teacher's speech. The essence of speech culture, the quality of scientific focus are largely determined by the skill of the teacher and in the future can become the basis for advanced and high-quality education in the training and education of future specialists.

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